

IP4OS

Protocol: A Scoping Review of Open Science and Intellectual Property Rights: Tensions, Synergies, and Best Practices

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Authors:

Name	Affiliation	ORCID
Gautam Sharma	Karolinska Institutet, Sweden	0000-0002-7908-706X
Julia Priess-Buchheit	Kiel University, Germany	0000-0003-3029-9683
Lea Škorić	University of Zagreb School of Medicine	0000-0002-1545-5791
Iva Čizmin	University of Zagreb School of Medicine	0009-0002-3787-1849
Frantzeska Papadopoulou Skarp	University of Stockholm, Law Faculty	0000-0003-1211-4972
Stephen Wyber	International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions	n/a
Pavel Stoev	National Museum of Natural History, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences and Pensoft Publishers	0000-0002-5702-5677
Anna-Lena Hansen	Kiel University, Germany	0000-0001-5806-9674
Gustav Nilsson	Karolinska Institutet, Sweden	0000-0001-5273-0150

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1. Abstract

Objectives: This scoping review aims to examine how open science practices and intellectual property frameworks interact, conflict with, or reinforce each other's objectives of knowledge dissemination and ownership protection within the context of knowledge valorisation and research commercialisation. It also aims to explore how these frameworks shape the development of research outputs, identifying both opportunities for synergy and structural barriers that may hinder the effective circulation of intellectual assets. This review further seeks to explore practical strategies for aligning intellectual property management with open science practices, ensuring that both frameworks can complement and mutually benefit each other in a way that fosters innovation, accessibility, and responsible knowledge governance.

Introduction: Open science practices and intellectual property frameworks play a crucial role in shaping how knowledge is created, shared, and protected in the research and innovation landscape. While open science aims to maximise accessibility and transparency, intellectual property rights are designed to regulate ownership and protection, often creating tensions between openness and exclusivity. Despite increasing attention to these dynamics, there remains a lack of comprehensive analysis that examines their interplay across different research domains and institutional settings. A scoping review that critically evaluates these interactions can provide new insights into how intellectual property frameworks can either support or hinder open science initiatives, highlighting pathways for alignment and strategies for mitigating conflicts.

Methods: A scoping review following the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines will be conducted to examine the interaction between open science practices and intellectual property frameworks. Key sources will include papers selected from Scopus and Web of Science, with additional relevant literature identified through hand-searches of reference lists from included papers and scoping reviews. The study selection process will involve an initial screening of titles and abstracts based on predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria. To be included, studies must explicitly address open science and its interaction with any aspect of intellectual property rights, including legal and economic dimensions. Eligible publication types will include all scientific documents. Studies without explicit discussions on intellectual property rights and open science and those with an exclusively technical focus will be excluded.

2. List of abbreviations

OS Open Science

IP Intellectual Property

IPR Intellectual Property Rights

ERA European Research Area

PRISMA Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses

WoS Web of Science

CSV Comma-Separated Values

3. Introduction

Open Science (OS) and Intellectual Property (IP) frameworks are increasingly shaping the landscape of research and innovation, influencing how knowledge is created, shared, protected and valorised. OS is an umbrella term covering various practices aimed at making research processes, data, analysis, and outputs more reproducible, understandable, and accessible (Spellman et al., 2017; Bornmann et al., 2021). OS practices, such as open-access publications, open code, and sharing data “as openly as possible, as closed as necessary”, seek to enhance research transparency and promote greater collaboration across disciplines and sectors, thereby increasing the overall impact of research (McKiernan et al., 2016). IP, on the other hand, refers to creations of the human mind, including inventions, literary and artistic works, designs, symbols, names, and images. Common forms of IP protection (Intellectual Property Rights) include patents, copyrights, trademarks, trade secrets, and industrial designs. IPRs primarily protect the rights of creators. However, this protection can sometimes limit access to scientific findings by granting exclusive rights, depending on how it is applied. This, in essence, creates a conflict with the principles of OS (Nuechterlein et al., 2023). Both IP and OS are increasingly utilised in scientific research to maximise their impact; however, their objectives can sometimes diverge. In some cases, they may operate in parallel, such as when core inventions are protected while derivatives are made openly available or when partial copyright and incomplete open access coexist. The European Research Area (ERA) has emphasised the importance of balancing IP management with OS principles to enhance knowledge valorisation, support innovation, and improve research accessibility. Despite these efforts, there remain significant challenges in aligning these two approaches, as IP laws support exclusivity, while OS promotes unrestricted access to knowledge. Existing studies have examined aspects of IP and OS separately, focusing on their respective benefits and limitations (Vincente-Saez & Martinez-Fuentes, 2018; Banks et al., 2019; Hargreaves, 2011; Holgersson & van Santen, 2018). However, few have systematically analysed how these frameworks interact, conflict, or complement each other in practice (de la Cueva and Méndez, 2022). There is a gap in understanding how different stakeholders—such as researchers, institutions, and policymakers—steer the tensions and opportunities between these frameworks across various research contexts. Moreover, while policy initiatives advocate for a concerted approach to IP and OS, there is limited empirical evidence on the effectiveness of these strategies in real-world settings. A scoping review is, therefore, well suited to address these gaps by synthesising existing research on the relationship between OS and IP frameworks. This review will examine areas of alignment and conflict, explore how different sectors and disciplines manage these interactions, and identify strategies and best practice examples documented in scientific literature to integrate both frameworks effectively. By analysing studies indexed in Scopus and Web of Science, this review aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the legal, economic, and practical dimensions of OS and IP, contributing to ongoing discussions on knowledge governance and research accessibility.

4. Review objectives

This scoping review has the following objectives:

1. To examine how IP frameworks and OS practices interact, identifying areas where they align, conflict, or create tensions in the management, dissemination and valorisation of research outputs.
2. To investigate how different stakeholders steer the relationship between OS and IP, assessing the legal, economic, and practical dimensions that shape their implementation across various research contexts.

3. To identify best practices mentioned in the literature for integrating IP with OS principles.

5. Keywords

Open science; intellectual property; knowledge valorisation; research dissemination; innovation governance; legal frameworks; data sharing; scholarly communication

6. Methods

6.1. Data sources and search strategy

The review will search the following databases to identify the relevant scientific documents: Scopus and Web of Science (WoS Core Collection All Editions). These databases have been selected for this scoping review due to their extensive and multidisciplinary coverage¹ of high-quality, peer-reviewed journals, ensuring the retrieval of reliable and relevant articles on a specific topic across diverse fields (Zhu & Liu, 2020). Their robust indexing and citation tracking capabilities make them credible and widely preferred for reviews, contributing to the methodological rigor of SLRs (Wanyama et al., 2022). In addition to articles retrieved from these databases, other relevant studies will also be included, such as those identified through the reference lists of selected papers or recommended by researchers involved in the project. These additional sources may not be indexed in Scopus or WoS but will be considered if they align with the objectives of this review. This approach follows the recommended practice of backward and forward snowballing to ensure comprehensive coverage of relevant literature in the field unless no further relevant articles are found (Wohlin, 2014).

A keyword search strategy will be used, combining Boolean operators (Table 1). The search will include “open science” OR “open peer review*” OR “open code” OR “open material*” OR “open data” OR “FAIR data” OR “data sharing” OR “open educational resources”. The term “open access” is excluded to avoid excessive irrelevant results, as many papers use it solely to indicate open-access publication. This inflates records and reduces precision. To capture studies on open access in copyright contexts, relevant papers will be manually identified through citation tracking and supplementary searches, ensuring its inclusion. This selection ensures that the retrieved literature covers key aspects of OS without being overly broad or fragmented.

Similarly, for IP, we use the keywords “intellectual property rights*” OR “Intellectual Property*” OR “IPR” OR “patent*” OR “copyright*” OR “trademark*” OR “trade secret*” OR “utility models” OR “technology transfer” OR “data rights” OR “open licenc*” OR “open licens*” to comprehensively capture the diverse legal mechanisms and strategies governing knowledge protection and dissemination.

Scopus search string: TITLE-ABS-KEY (“open science” OR “open peer review*” OR “open code” OR “open material*” OR “open data” OR “FAIR data” OR “data sharing” OR “open educational resources”) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (“intellectual property rights*” OR “Intellectual Property*” OR “IPR” OR “patent*” OR “copyright*” OR “trademark*” OR “trade secret*” OR “utility models” OR “technology transfer” OR “data rights” OR “open licenc*” OR “open licens*”)

Web of Science search string: TS=(“open science” OR “open peer review*” OR “open code” OR “open material*” OR “open data” OR “FAIR data” OR “data sharing” OR “open educational resources”) AND TS=(“intellectual property rights*” OR “Intellectual Property*” OR “IPR” OR “patent*” OR “copyright*” OR “trademark*” OR “trade secret*” OR “utility models” OR “technology transfer” OR “data rights” OR “open licenc*” OR “open licens*”)

¹ While Scopus and Web of Science (WoS) are widely used for academic indexing, many law journals are not included, as legal research is often found in specialized databases.

Table 1: Keyword search strategy

Topic	Keywords
Open Science	“open science” OR “open peer review*” OR “open code” OR “open material*” OR “open data” OR “FAIR data” OR “data sharing” OR “open educational resources”
Intellectual Property	“intellectual property rights*” OR “Intellectual Propert*” OR “IPR” OR “patent*” OR “copyright*” OR “trademark*” OR “trade secret*” OR “utility models” OR “technology transfer” OR “data rights” OR “open licenc*” OR “open licens*”

Our review will not impose a time limitation, ensuring a comprehensive analysis of how the interaction between OS and IP has evolved over time, including historical developments, policy shifts, and emerging trends. It will also include all types of scholarly outputs, such as research articles, book chapters, conference proceedings, books, and editorials to capture a diverse range of perspectives, from theoretical discussions to practical implementation.

6.2. Screening and eligibility criteria

One author will conduct the initial search in the databases and export the results in the form of either a CSV or excel sheet, which will then be used for removing the duplicates. The first stage of screening will involve reading the titles and abstracts of the papers which will be done by two authors. The papers selected in this stage will then be read in full. These are recommended procedures followed in other SLRs (Salim et al., 2019; Haldar et al., 2023). Two authors will independently screen all the articles and determine their eligibility for review. Any article excluded from the final review will have its reason for exclusion recorded to ensure transparency in the selection process. Any disagreements in this process regarding inclusion/exclusion of a certain article will be settled through discussion. The whole process of screening and selecting the articles will be illustrated using the PRISMA flowchart.

To be included in the review, papers must examine the relationship between OS practices and IP frameworks, specifically addressing areas of interaction, conflict, or alignment in knowledge dissemination and ownership protection. Studies must explore legal or economic dimensions of the relationship between OS and IP rights, focusing on their impact on research dissemination and accessibility as well as on innovation. As mentioned earlier, eligible publications will include all types of documents indexed in these databases. Papers will be excluded if they do not explicitly discuss both OS and IP frameworks.

Figure 1: PRISMA workflow (Page et al., 2021)

6.3. Data extraction and analysis

For data extraction, a structured framework will be employed to systematically capture key bibliographic, contextual, methodological, and thematic elements from each included document. The extracted information will include basic publication details such as article title, type of article, journal or conference name, year, and author affiliations, enabling an assessment of geographical and disciplinary trends. The contextuality of the study and its keywords will help define its thematic focus, while the discipline or field of study will be determined based on author affiliations and the journal's scope. To classify research approaches, the type of study (conceptual, empirical, theoretical, or review) and methodology (qualitative, quantitative, mixed methods, or none mentioned) will be recorded. Relevant OS practices, such as open access mandates and open data repositories, and IP instruments, such as copyrights, patents, and licenses, will be identified. Lastly, key challenges described in the paper regarding OS and IP interactions, proposed solutions, and any best practices will be extracted. Thus, each paper will be assessed for its suitability for

inclusion in the mapping exercise, ensuring that only the most relevant studies contribute to the synthesis.

For data analysis, Clarke and Braun's (2017) thematic analysis will be employed to systematically identify patterns, themes, and insights within the extracted data. This method ensures a rigorous and flexible approach to analysing qualitative data, allowing for the identification of recurring concepts and relationships within the literature. Thematic coding will be conducted in an iterative manner, where key themes related to the interaction between OS and IP will be identified, refined, and categorised. The results will be organised into three main areas: areas of tension, practical strategies for reconciliation, and best practices. The analysis will also help us find the spheres where IP-OS synergy might not work. Areas of tension will highlight conflicting mandates, legal ambiguities, and institutional challenges that arise when aligning OS principles with IP frameworks. Practical strategies for reconciliation will include approaches such as policy adaptations, licensing mechanisms, and collaborative governance models that have been proposed or implemented to bridge these gaps. Best practices will showcase successful case studies, institutional policies, and regulatory frameworks that effectively integrate IP management with OS principles.

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